

Reproducibility Study: Web2Text

THOMAS NIEDERMAYER, FABIAN TRAXLER, and MAGNUS WAGNER, Vienna University of Technology, Austria

Reproducibility describes the ability to replicate research results in the same research setting. Ensuring reproducibility of research in computer science is key to enable further scientific advances based on the findings. For this study, we analyse the paper “Web2Text: Deep Structured Boilerplate Removal” (2018) of Vogels et al. on its reproducibility. Boilerplate removal is an important step of information retrieval where the main content of a web page is stripped from its navigational content. We generate bootstrap samples of the original data set and retrain the model on each one to confirm that the published performance results are within a certain confidence interval. As a second step, we test the pre-trained model performance on a modern web page data set and compare the results to other algorithms that were used as a baseline for the original data set. In summary, the results of the paper can be confirmed. On the modern data set, the Web2Text model outperforms the other algorithms as well. For the reproduction of this paper, the provision of code and data with instructions on how to run the code was crucial.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: reproducibility study, boilerplate removal, information retrieval, experiment design, convolutional neural network, CleanEval, GoogleTrends-2017

ACM Reference Format:

Thomas Niedermayer, Fabian Traxler, and Magnus Wagner. 2021. Reproducibility Study: Web2Text. 1, 1 (January 2021), 6 pages. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4459468>

1 INTRODUCTION

In the process of science, ensuring reproducibility is an important step to make research comprehensible and relevant. Reproducibility refers to the ability of a researcher to generate the same results with the same experiment design and methods as were used by the original scientist. It is “a minimum necessary condition for a finding to be believable and informative” and is only possible, if the original research goes into enough detail on how the methods were applied and the results were acquired [Cacioppo et al. 2015]. Only then, the procedures can be exactly repeated. In contrast, replicability describes the ability to duplicate results by using the original procedures on a comparable research setting. Its difficulty increases with a higher randomness in the generation of results but for deterministic systems, it should be comparably difficult as reproducibility [Goodman et al. 2016]. For most disciplines of science, there is also a peer-review process upstream of the publication of a paper to assess the quality and use the reviewers’ comments to refine the article. If reproducibility is lacking, a thorough understanding of the work is not possible and might lead to a rejection of the paper.

In many fields, projects to test a large sample of papers on reproducibility concluded that results can often not be reproduced with the same significance or at all [Baker 2016; Begley and Ellis 2012; Nosek et al. 2015]. Even in computer science, which is commonly

considered a more deterministic research environment, there are often found reproducibility issues. In a reproducibility study conducted by Hutson about artificial intelligence research, just 6 % of the papers included code, only 30 % included test data and 54 % at least included pseudo code, which is not optimal but helps in understanding the algorithms. This still leaves a minimum of 40 % of research papers in the study that did not describe their code in any detail at all which makes it especially hard to reproduce their results. [Hutson 2018] Providing code and data set as well as describing every procedure in enough detail could be considered the “gold standard” of reproducibility [Peng 2011]. A further addition would be the more modern concept of *Evaluation-as-a-Service (EaaS)* which deals with issues like data privacy, an ever increasing size of data sets and different runtime environments by hosting data sets on a platform that allows access via APIs or virtual machines to apply algorithms on the data sets [Hanbury et al. 2015].

For this study, we decided to analyse the paper “Web2Text: Deep Structured Boilerplate Removal” (2018) by Vogels, Ganea and Eickhoff on its reproducibility [Vogels et al. 2018]. It was published as a conference paper for the *European Conference on Information Retrieval*. Information Retrieval is a discipline of computer science which deals with finding useful information from large collections of data. A common example is a search engine. In information retrieval, the need for reproducibility shows in the need for baseline results of commonly used search algorithms and ranking functions with common data sets. Some studies showed significant differences in performance between allegedly similar algorithms on different systems [Mühleisen et al. 2014; Trotman et al. 2014]. Therefore, an analysis on reproducibility in information retrieval papers is sensible.

2 WEB2TEXT: USED ALGORITHMS

The chosen paper deals with the aspect of boiler plate removal which is the task of stripping website content of its navigational text. In the context of information retrieval, it can significantly improve the performance of search engines. Boilerplate removal often relies on rule-based methods to decide between main content and navigational content. The Web2Text paper chose to approach the task with predictions from two convolutional neural networks (CNNs) after preprocessing the input data. For the preprocessing, the HTML files are parsed as Document Object Model (DOM) trees. Those trees are refined by removing empty nodes and merging single child parent nodes to create a collapsed DOM structure (CDOM). Each resulting leaf is either labeled as main content or navigational content. For each leaf, 128 features are collected that can be fed into the first CNN. Additionally, for each pair of neighboring leaves, 25 edge features are collected that will be processed with the second CNN. Convolutional neural networks are a type of deep neural networks that prevent overfitting by aggregating a large number of

Authors’ address: Thomas Niedermayer, 01600968@student.tuwien.ac.at; Fabian Traxler, e1553958@student.tuwien.ac.at; Magnus Wagner, e12034922@student.tuwien.ac.at, Vienna University of Technology, Karlsplatz 13, 1040 Vienna, Vienna, Austria, 1040.

inputs through different filters. In the case of HTML documents, neighboring text blocks influence the probability of being main or navigational content and are incorporated with the use of convolutional layers. The CNN focusing on single leaf features outputs a probability for the block being main content. The CNN focusing on pairwise leaf features outputs probabilities for different possible transitions (main-to-navigational, main-to-main etc.). For inference, a weighted product of single and pairwise probabilities is maximized with the Viterbi algorithm. This is possible as the product represents a hidden markov model in its form. The Viterbi algorithm removes the need to calculate the probability for every sequence of labels in a document. It uses dynamic programming to make the probability maximization computationally more feasible. The label sequence with the highest probability is chosen as a result.

3 DATA

Data sets for the task of boilerplate removal consist, like for other supervised learning tasks, of raw data and their respective ground truth labels. In context of boilerplate removal the raw data is an HTML-Page, like those found in the World Wide Web, and the label is the main content of this page as text. One important aspect of reproducibility is the data used in the experiments. For Web2Text, two different web page data sets have been used.

3.1 CleanEval Dataset

The CleanEval dataset [Baroni et al. 2008] is readily accessible and small which makes it easy to handle. It consists of 737 HTML Pages and the respective main content manually extracted as text-files. More information can be found in the CleanEval Challenge Paper [Baroni et al. 2008] or in the Web2Text Paper [Vogels et al. 2018].

3.2 ClueWeb12 Dataset

3.2.1 Solving the Problem of too big data. Regarding the ClueWeb12 dataset [Evgeniy Gabrilovich, Michael Ringgaard, and Amarnag Subramanya 2013] we have concerns about the feasibility of carrying out the same steps as in the paper because of the sheer amount of data used. Additionally, the data is not accessible for free, as the Carnegie Mellon University distributes it to recipients that meet their formal criteria by sending mails containing hard drives with ClueWeb12 in storage. An online article of [National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine 2019] defines reproducibility and replicability as follows:

"Reproducibility means obtaining consistent computational results using the same input data, computational steps, methods, code, and conditions of analysis. Replicability means obtaining consistent results across studies aimed at answering the same scientific question, each of which has obtained its own data."

One could follow the method described in [Vogels et al. 2018] with reduced data, but from an experiment design view, this would mean changing another independent variable and thus not making it a full reproduction. For an examination of replicability this would still be a viable way to carry out the experiment with weaker computational

power, as the question "does boilerplate removal help in information retrieval" could still be answered.

3.3 Estimating required computational resources

In theory, experiments with high computational demands can still be reproduced. However, the problem is different to other challenges in reproducibility. An example is the versioning of software components. With increasing computational demands it continuously excludes entities from the pool of entities that are able to reproduce the experiment. We try to quantify the reproducibility impairment by estimating the computational resources required. More specifically, we have a look at the data used to measure the impact on the retrieval performance, as the training and testing done on the CleanEval dataset is documented in detail including runtime and the machine it was run on. We consider training and prediction times, assuming calculation of the metrics to be negligible. Assuming CleanEval and ClueWeb12 contain webpages of similar size, it takes about $733.000.000 \cdot 0.054$ seconds on the MacBook with a 2.8 GHz Intel Core i5 used in the Web2Text paper to apply the boilerplate removal. After that, the data has to be indexed twice. Once for the approach using Web2Text and once for the approach without boilerplate removal. According to a website of the Indri search engine¹, 24 machines with 2 Intel Xeon 3.2 GHz CPUs (undisclosed core count, for simplicity we assume the same count as in the MacBook) and 1 TB disc storage take 67 days for about 1.000.000.000 documents and 30 days for about 500.000.000 documents. Interpolating linearly gives a runtime of roughly 48 days for the ClueWeb12 dataset. Parallelising the boilerplate removal on 48 3.2 GHz CPUs would result in at least 8 days of processing. In total 104 days of computation on 48 CPUs would have to be done for the ClueWeb12 dataset. CW12-B, which is about 7% of ClueWeb12's data obtained by random sampling of ClueWeb12 needs to be considered too. Trying to account for the fact that indexing is faster with smaller data we estimate the total time of computation to be at least 107 days on 24 machines with 2 3.2GHz CPUs. This leaves the required hard discs and RAM unaccounted for, but gives an estimation of a lower boundary for what is required to replicate the Web2Text paper. Our estimation makes it clear that regarding temporal and financial requirements, some entities could already be prevented from reproducing the experiments if the initial computation attempt is successful and is not interrupted.

3.4 GoogleTrends-2017 dataset

As the CleanEval dataset is already quite old and web technologies are changing, one independent variable that could potentially change over time is the way boilerplates are structured. So to check how well the Web2Text generalises, a more recent dataset like GoogleTrends-2017 (GT17) [Leonhardt et al. 2020] should be used.

4 REPRODUCTION

4.1 Rerunning the experiments

The code used to conduct the experiments was provided by the authors in a GitHub repository. We forked their repository to add

¹<https://lemurproject.org/clueweb09/indri-howto.php>

our own ²code. As described in the paper, the experiment was implemented using two programming languages: Scala, for extracting the block and edge features of each HTML document, and Python, used for training the CNN as well as predicting the block labels using the trained CNN and the Viterbi Algorithm.

The provided instructions in the GitHub Repository only described how to use the code to classify a new HTML Page provided by the user. However, there was no description of the steps needed in order to rerun the experiment pipeline with the CleanEval dataset. Therefore, a closer look at the code was necessary.

First, the used programming languages and library version had to be determined to get the best matching results. In addition to the GitHub repository, the authors provided a Docker container which contained the used Scala and SBT versions. However, the Python + Python library versions have not been stated in the paper or the code. Fortunately, the repository contains a link to a blog post which describes how to run the code for a single HTML page. This post also states the library versions for Numpy and Tensorflow that should work. Therefore, we decided to conduct our experiments with the same versions and use the latest *click* version:

```
numpy == 1.18.0
tensorflow == 1.15.0
tensorflow-gpu == 1.15.0
click == 7.1.2
```

The first step is to transform the CleanEval dataset into a set of block and edge features (multiple blocks per page). This can be done using the provided docker container and the available code. There have been a few things to take into consideration: First, there was no documentation that showed how to access and transform the whole dataset at once. After analyzing the Scala code and the comments we realized that the Main class of the Scala program was intended to transform the CleanEval dataset in one step. We only needed to change the path of the folders in which the csv-files are to be placed and the CleanEval dataset to be found, since this was an absolute path on one of the authors machines. After changing the path to one present in the dockers filesystem the code could be run using this command:

```
sbt "runMain ch.ethz.dalab.web2text.Main"
```

After running this command two csv-files are produced which contain the block-features and the edge-features for every block in every HTML page. The next step is to transform the csv-files into one Numpy file that can be accessed faster within the python program. The necessary script is located in:

```
src/main/python/data/convert_scala_csv.py
```

Finally, the two CNNs can be trained using the feature set. Both networks are created and trained using Tensorflow. The training process can be done using the script located at `src/main/python.main.py` with the argument `train_unary` or `train_edge` respectively. After training, both networks are saved to disc and can then be used for inference and to evaluate the performance. This is also done using the script `src/main/python/main.py` with the argument

`test_structured`. The default option is to use the data split provided by the CleanEval dataset (train: 55 pages, validation: 5 pages, test: 676p pages). After running the pipeline described above we were able to obtain the following results:

Running Times (Training) - Intel I7-8700K, no CUDA:

- (1) Feature Extraction: 23s
- (2) Unary CNN: 28.08s
- (3) Edge CNN: 22.62s

Metric	Both CNNs	Only Unary CNN
Accuracy	0.841 (0.84)	0.849
Recall	0.880 (0.85)	0.903
Precision	0.856 (0.88)	0.850
F1 Score	0.868 (0.86)	0.867

Table 1. Reproduced results of Web2Text Algorithm

The results shown in Table 1 are very similar to the reported results (shown in the brackets) in the paper. However, when using only the Unary-CNN and completely discarding the edge features, we interestingly do not lose much model performance. The next step is to check for the stability of the results and if there is a significant performance loss using only the Unary-CNN.

4.2 Confirming the results

The next step after rerunning the results was to validate that these results are indeed correct and representative. Since the results in the paper only focused on the split given in the CleanEval Challenge [Baroni et al. 2008], it is not guaranteed that the obtained results are caused by the power of the algorithm but rather from a lucky split. Furthermore, the authors also proposed a different data split ("Web2Text Split"), which introduced more training data and therefore less test data (531 train, 58 validation, 148 test).

4.2.1 Generating representative results. In order to generate expressive results we relied on the bootstrapping method to generate multiple random splits of the original dataset. Therefore, we first generated the features of all pages provided by the CleanEval dataset like described in section 4.1 using the Scala implementation of the Web2Text algorithm. Next, we implemented a Python Script which performs a random split of the dataset with the same size as in the CleanEval Challenge - 55 pages for training, 5 for validation and 673 for testing. With these generated splits we reused the Python module provided by the authors of Web2Text in order to train and test the model. In order to get meaningful results we generated 100 of these random splits and therefore obtained 100 results with different training and test data. We use these bootstrapped results to test if the reported performance measures are statistically valid (meaning they do not rely on a lucky split) and if the performance of the Web2Text algorithm is statistically better than the other algorithms shown in the paper.

4.2.2 Significance testing. Table 1 in the inspected paper displays accuracy, precision, recall and F1 Score for Web2Text and competing algorithms. What we are testing here is whether the metrics stated

²<https://github.com/Tommel71/web2text/tree/experiment-design>

in the paper belong to the distribution of the metrics we got from bootstrapping. We cannot use a t-test because we only have one observation which would result in 0 degrees of freedom, and the t-test checks for differences in means where we only have one observation in one of the two samples. So we use the empirical distribution we got from the bootstrapping and formulate the null hypothesis for each metric as follows: "The metric found in the paper originates from the distribution of the metric yielded by the bootstrapping". Under this assumption, we define the p-value as the percentage of observations in the bootstrap metrics that have the same value or a more extreme one than the observation in the paper. The measure of extremeness is 2 times the minimum of the percentage of observations above and the percentage of the elements below the metric stated in the paper. In this case, a lower measure of extremeness means more extreme. The alternative hypothesis is that the metric from the paper does not come from the same distribution and we are testing for both sides at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. This is also visualised in Figure 1 for the accuracy metric.

Fig. 1. Accuracies measured of 100 bootstrap samples from the CleanEval split. The part colored in red marks the lowest 2.5% and highest 2.5% of observations. Observations in this area have a p value smaller than 0.05.

Metric	Score in Web2Text	p-value	Significant
Accuracy	0.84	0.86	no
Recall	0.85	0.44	no
Precision	0.88	0.20	no
F1 Score	0.86	0.62	no

Table 2. Significance test of the metrics in Web2Text belonging to the bootstrap distribution of metrics we got for the CleanEval split.

Our conclusion is that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected in any of the cases and thus the results stated in the paper are reasonable.

Metric	Score in Web2Text	p-value	Significant
Accuracy	0.84	0.82	no
Recall	0.85	0.94	no
Precision	0.88	0.76	no
F1 Score	0.86	0.98	no

Table 3. Similar to Table 2 significance tests for the Web2Text split.

4.2.3 *Structured vs Unary results.* In an effort to test the robustness of the Web2Text method we also evaluated the approach with just the unary network. Figure 2 shows the accuracy of the two methods on the same 100 bootstrap samples of 55 training pages, 5 validation pages and 673 test pages. Table 4 contains results of a pairwise t-test where the null hypothesis is that the two approaches perform equally well. The alternative hypothesis is that the structured approach performs better. The tests are mostly significant and the implication is that the structured CNN is indeed helping and makes sense to be included.

Fig. 2. Structured vs. unary network accuracy.

Metric	Structured	Unary	p value	Significant
Accuracy	0.836	0.828	0.002	yes
Recall	0.876	0.856	0.000	yes
Precision	0.850	0.852	0.818	no
F1 Score	0.862	0.852	0.000	yes

Table 4. Mean of metrics and p value.

4.3 Generalisation power of Web2Text

Another very important characteristic of machine learning algorithms is the generalisation power, which means if they also perform

well on unseen data. This is, on the one hand, evaluated using a validation/test set but since all data from these subsets come from the same source we decided it would be better to test the algorithm on a totally different dataset. Since we were not able to obtain results for the ClueWeb12 dataset because we did not have the necessary computing power we decided to test the algorithm on GT17. To convert the data to a form that is usable for Web2Text, some assumptions had to be made. Firstly, there are tags like `<l>`, `<h>` and `<p>` at the beginning of new blocks in the boilerplate-removed data of CleanEval, that do not have a documented meaning and no obvious pattern for usage. Furthermore, there is irregular whitespace that could have meaning, but as it is not documented we assumed it to be irrelevant for the procedure. In the algorithm, all three tags are removed and the file is trimmed when loading them into the memory before calculating performance. We decided to only use `<p>` at the beginning of blocks, as it does not matter which tag is present. After extracting boilerplate-less data from GT17 in a way that roughly matches the CleanEval structure, we used the alignment algorithm implemented in the Web2Text repository, and excluded 2 pages due to a memory error during the algorithm. After preprocessing the data, the feature extraction approach of Web2Text was used, which produced features for every block of every HTML page of GT17. In this process however, another 5 pages of the dataset had to be deleted due to errors in the feature-extraction algorithm. Therefore, 172 HTML pages with features and labels for every block were obtained, which could be used for the classification part of the Web2Text algorithm.

4.3.1 Using the Web2Text Network on GT17. The first approach was to use the provided pretrained networks, which can be found in the GitHub repository of the Web2Text paper. Since the authors trained two networks, one with the original CleanEval Split (55 train, 5 val, 673 test) and one with their own split (531 train, 5 val, 144 test), we tested both networks. Therefore, we used all 172 pages of the GoogleTrends-2017 dataset to obtain the results shown in Table 5.

Algorithm	Test Set	Accu.	Prec.	Recall	F1
Web2Text-55	GT17	0.86	0.90	0.86	0.88
Web2Text-531	GT17	0.88	0.88	0.90	0.89
BTE	GT17	0.80	0.25	0.72	0.37
BP-Article	GT17	0.90	0.40	0.51	0.45
BP-Largest	GT17	0.90	0.35	0.32	0.33
BP-Default	GT17	0.83	0.26	0.59	0.36
Unfluff	GT17	0.91	0.45	0.36	0.40

Table 5. Performance on the GoogleTrends-2017 Dataset

4.3.2 Training and Validation with GoogleTrends-2017. The next interesting question is if Web2text also performs as good if trained on the new dataset. Therefore, we did not use the pretrained models but used the same bootstrap approach as above in which we sample 55 training pages (+5 validation pages) to train the CNNs and then use the remaining 112 pages to test the algorithm. Again we generated 100 random splits of the data and trained and tested the algorithm. The boxplots in Figure 3 show the metrics of Web2Text on the 100

bootstrap samples. The metrics of GT17 are in the same ballpark as the metrics of CleanEval, thus giving us reason to believe that the generalisation power of Web2Text is good.

Fig. 3. Boxplots of metrics of Web2Text trained and evaluated on CleanEval and GT17

4.4 Relative Performance to other presented algorithms

In the Web2Text paper, the performance results were compared with other boilerplate removal algorithms. Many of those have a heuristic approach while the *Victor* algorithm needs a trained model to perform. It was decided to focus on the rule-based methods to confirm the presented values from the paper and to test them on GT17. The chosen algorithms are "Body Text Extraction" (BTE) [Finn et al. 2001], "Boilerpipe" in the three variants "default-extractor", "article extractor" and "largest-content-extractor" [Kohlschütter et al. 2010] and the "Unfluff" algorithm [Geitgey 2014]. Those algorithms were already imported from the respective repositories or as Java packages and could be found in the Web2Text repository. After some custom installation steps, the results could be generated for the CleanEval test set specified by the Web2Text authors and the whole GT17 data set. For the newer data set, performance was measured on all samples as there is no training set necessary for the heuristic approaches. Afterwards, all generated results were aligned with the original files and labels could be extracted. Due to several issues with the alignment algorithm on GT17, some exception handling was inserted into the code. Files, that could not be aligned, were skipped. In Table 6, it can be observed that the exact results could be reproduced for the CleanEval test set. The performance of other methods stated in the Web2Text paper is therefore confirmed.

In Table 5, the comparison between Web2Text and the other frameworks on GT17 gives more insight. Concerning accuracy, all algorithms perform comparably well. Some older frameworks show an even better accuracy than the Web2Text-531 model. Regarding the other metrics, the rule-based algorithms perform far worse. This

can be explained in two ways. One issue is the correct identification of main content as the recall values are very low. This might be due to the change in typical characteristics of web pages from 2007 to 2017. Several new features were introduced with HTML5 in 2014 which have not been incorporated into older algorithms. The rule-based algorithms could therefore not keep up with identifying what is main content. The second issue is the low precision. This metric is drastically lower due to a much larger share of navigational content in the newer data set. While the CleanEval test set contains 59.0 % main content, only 8.1 % of the GT17 blocks are labeled as main content. So although the share of true negative to false positive results stayed similar over both data sets, the larger amount of navigational content results in a much worse precision which is the share of true positive results to all positive results. In contrast, the Web2Text model trained on the CleanEval data set is much more reliable in dealing with this abundance of navigational content in modern websites.

Algorithm	Test Set	Accu.	Prec.	Recall	F1
BTE	Orig. CE	0.79	0.79	0.89	0.83
BTE	Rep. CE	0.79	0.79	0.89	0.83
BP-Article	Orig. CE	0.72	0.91	0.59	0.71
BP-Article	Rep. CE	0.72	0.91	0.59	0.71
BP-Largest	Orig. CE	0.60	0.93	0.36	0.52
BP-Largest	Orig. CE	0.60	0.93	0.36	0.52
BP-Default	Orig. CE	0.80	0.89	0.75	0.81
BP-Default	Orig. CE	0.80	0.89	0.75	0.81
Unfluff	Orig. CE	0.71	0.90	0.57	0.70
Unfluff	Orig. CE	0.71	0.90	0.57	0.70

Table 6. Comparison between stated and reproduced performance of other frameworks on CleanEval.

5 CONCLUSION

When reconstructing the results in the paper, the code that came with Web2Text was of great help. We put the implementation to the test using bootstrap sampling and statistical tests and found out that the metrics stated are realistic. Furthermore we put the data under scrutiny and decided that the part involving ClueWeb12 is infeasible for us to test and we argued why this impairs reproducibility. We explored different splits of the CleanEval dataset and expanded on the paper by adding a more recent boilerplate removal dataset - GT17 - to the comparison. We found that Web2Text generalises well enough to yield good results on GT17, both when trained on CleanEval and when trained on GT17. Examining metrics for both the structured as well as the unary method shows that the structured method is a sensible expansion of the algorithm. The comparison of Web2Text with other frameworks was transparent and the relative performance difference could be replicated on the GT17 dataset. The author of the paper even linked to newer boilerplate removal algorithms than Web2Text in the GitHub repository to make a comparison possible. While many parts of the inner workings of the procedure and parts

of the requirements are undocumented, we believe that this paper shows good reproducibility.

REFERENCES

- Monya Baker. 2016. 1,500 scientists lift the lid on reproducibility. (2016).
- Marco Baroni, Francis Chantree, Adam Kilgarriff, and Serge Sharoff. 2008. CleanEval: a Competition for Cleaning Web Pages. In *Proceedings of the Sixth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC'08)*. European Language Resources Association (ELRA), Marrakech, Morocco. http://www.lrec-conf.org/proceedings/lrec2008/pdf/162_paper.pdf
- C Glenn Begley and Lee M Ellis. 2012. Raise standards for preclinical cancer research. *Nature* 483, 7391 (2012), 531–533.
- John T Cacioppo, Robert M Kaplan, Jon A Krosnick, James L Olds, and Heather Dean. 2015. Social, Behavioral, and Economic Sciences Perspectives on Robust and Reliable Science. (2015).
- Evgeniy Gabrilovich, Michael Ringgaard, and Amarnag Subramanya. 2013. FACC1: Freebase annotation of ClueWeb corpora, Version 1 (Release date 2013-06-26, Format version 1, Correction level 0). <http://lemurproject.org/clueweb12/>
- Aidan Finn, Nicholas Kushmerick, and Barry Smyth. 2001. Fact or Fiction: Content Classification for Digital Libraries.. In *DELOS*.
- Adam Geitgey. 2014. Unfluff – an automatic web page content extractor for node.js.
- Steven N Goodman, Daniele Fanelli, and John PA Ioannidis. 2016. What does research reproducibility mean? *Science translational medicine* 8, 341 (2016), 341ps12–341ps12.
- Allan Hanbury, Henning Müller, Krisztian Balog, Torben Brodt, Gordon V Cormack, Ivan Eggel, Tim Gollub, Frank Hopfgartner, Jayashree Kalpathy-Cramer, Noriko Kando, et al. 2015. Evaluation-as-a-service: Overview and outlook. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1512.07454* (2015).
- Matthew Hutson. 2018. Artificial intelligence faces reproducibility crisis.
- Christian Kohlschütter et al. 2010. Boilerpipe–boilerplate removal and fulltext extraction from HTML pages. *Google Code* (2010).
- Jurek Leonhardt, Avishek Anand, and Megha Khosla. 2020. Boilerplate Removal using a Neural Sequence Labeling Model. *Companion Proceedings of the Web Conference 2020* (Apr 2020). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3366424.3383547>
- Hannes Mühleisen, Thaeer Samar, Jimmy Lin, and Arjen De Vries. 2014. Old dogs are great at new tricks: Column stores for IR prototyping. In *Proceedings of the 37th international ACM SIGIR conference on Research & development in information retrieval*. 863–866.
- National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. 2019. New report examines reproducibility and replicability in science. <https://phys.org/news/2019-05-replicability-science.html#:~:text=Reproducibility%20means%20obtaining%20consistent%20computational,has%20obtained%20its%20own%20data>.
- Brian A Nosek, Alexander A Aarts, Joanna E Anderson, Heather Barry Kappes, Open Science Collaboration, et al. 2015. Estimating the reproducibility of psychological science. *Science* 349, 6251 (2015), aac4716–aac4716.
- Roger D Peng. 2011. Reproducible research in computational science. *Science* 334, 6060 (2011), 1226–1227.
- Andrew Trotman, Antti Puurula, and Blake Burgess. 2014. Improvements to BM25 and language models examined. In *Proceedings of the 2014 Australasian Document Computing Symposium*. 58–65.
- Thijs Vogels, Octavian-Eugen Ganea, and Carsten Eickhoff. 2018. Web2Text: Deep Structured Boilerplate Removal. *arXiv:1801.02607* [cs.IR]